

Shrinking Green Footprint in Future Urbanism: Urban Green Space Analysis and Monitoring Using Remote Sensing Data

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Abstract

The rapid expansion of urbanization globally, has resulted in gradual disappearance of green spaces, threatening the quality of urban life and environmental sustainability. Conventional methods like Field Surveys, Aerial Photography and Satellite Imagery, fail to capture real-time data for effective urban planning and management. This study explores innovative solutions, harnessing remote sensing and GIS technology, to combat the diminishing urban green footprints. Through effective integration of these tools, we aim for precise urban green space assessments, tracking transformations and empowering planners. Thereby, promising substantial green space preservation, to enhance urban resilience. This research connects remote sensing, GIS and architecture/planning, empowering decision-makers with timely insights. This study investigates three cases of diverse urban landscapes - Bangalore, Singapore and Abu Dhabi, to ensure the applicability and versatility of the proposed solution in varied urban contexts. This study concludes with a focus on policy proposals and minor interventions, to facilitate sustainable urban growth.

Keywords: *urbanization, green spaces, life quality, environmental sustainability, urban planning.*

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Introduction

In the face of rapid urbanization, understanding the dynamic interplay between urban growth and preservation of green spaces, has never been more critical. This chapter delves into the pressing issue of shrinking green footprints, proceeding further into future urbanism, offering a comprehensive analysis of urban green spaces and their monitoring, through the lens of remote sensing data. In concurrence with different research works, this chapter also embarks on a journey to unravel the multifaceted dimensions of urban green spaces. Urban green spaces have emerged as pivotal elements of sustainable development, enriching the quality of life for its residents, while promoting ecological well-being. The need to protect and expand these oases of nature, within the concrete jungles of contemporary cities is evident. The European Urban Green Infrastructure Network, as discussed in "Social Perspectives on

Urban Green Blue Grids" (Urban Green-Blue Grids, n.d.), emphasizes on the social significance of green spaces in fostering sustainable and vibrant communities.

Furthermore, "Urban Green Spaces: Combining Goals for Sustainability and Place-making" (Europe Now, 2021) explores the intricate balance between sustainability and place-making in urban green space design, offering insights into the challenges and opportunities faced by modern urban planners and designers. Amid this discourse, remote sensing data emerges as a powerful tool for monitoring urban green spaces. "The Importance of Urban Greening" (Viriotopia Team, 2018) highlights the significance of harnessing technology to assess and manage urban green spaces effectively.

Incorporating the techniques from the research findings in "Monitoring Urban Green Spaces Using Remote Sensing and GIS" (Vatseva, et al., 2016), this chapter investigates how remote sensing techniques can provide valuable insights into the state of urban green spaces, paving the way for informed decision-making and sustainable urban planning. As we navigate the complex landscape of urbanization, this chapter sets the stage for a deeper exploration of the challenges and opportunities surrounding urban green spaces and the pivotal role that remote sensing data plays in their analysis and preservation.

Purpose of Study

The study provides methods to identify areas with inadequate green infrastructure, prioritize locations for new parks or green areas, and develop strategies to enhance the accessibility and quality of existing urban green spaces, by tracking the changes over time, such as land-use conversions, encroachments or degradation of green areas. Identifying potential threats to urban green spaces, can help in implementing timely interventions, to mitigate these issues through policy making. Town Planners can gain a comprehensive understanding of the spatial distribution, extent and quality of urban green spaces. This information enables evidence-based decision making and effective management strategies.

Methodology

Three popular cities have been identified for study, based on certain parameters. The criteria for listing are influenced by the type and purpose of its study. The datasets of Landsat 8 and 9 for the Temporal Analysis for the year 2003, 2013 and 2023 have been downloaded from USGS Explorer, for the chosen cities. The datasets should have the bands required for the study, i.e. Band 4 (Red) and Band 5 (NIR). NDVI (Normalised Difference Vegetation Index) have been used to analyze the urban green spaces. NDVI formula used here, is $[(NIR - Red) / (NIR + Red)]$ or $[(Band\ 5 - Band\ 4) / (Band\ 5 + Band\ 4)]$. The output is then classified into unique values with equal intervals. NDVI value always ranges from -1 to +1, where 1 being the most densely vegetated areas and -1 being deep water areas. The areas with value 0.3 and higher have been considered to be vegetated areas and only such areas have been extracted using Raster Calculator. The difference of shrinkage or growth have been observed, and further related study is done. Progressive study here, includes the history of Urban Green Spaces and the impact of urbanization on the green spaces of all the three cities (chosen sites), the factors responsible for the changes and the policies implemented to overcome the challenge of shrinking Urban Green Spaces. The study is then concluded after comparing the three sites and their inferences.

Sites of Study

The sites of study have been chosen based on two major parameters, the first being temporal change in their Urban green spaces and the second, their progress and development stage, as a city. Abu Dhabi being a developed city in the Middle-eastern desert, has very few urban green spaces. Bangalore is a developing city with a good amount of urban green spaces, popularly known as the Garden City of India. And Singapore is a developed city, an Island country, with a good amount of urban green spaces.

Case Study 1 – Bangalore

Figure 1. NDVI Temporal Analysis of Bangalore City for 2003, 2013, 2023.

The Urban Greens and the Impact of Urbanisation on them

Between 2003 and 2023, Bangalore underwent a dramatic transformation fueled by rapid urbanization, significantly affecting its urban green spaces. Research from "Urban Blue-Green Conundrum: 10 City Study on Impacts of Urbanization on Natural Infrastructure in India" (Goswami, et al., 2022) , highlights that the city experienced a marked reduction in its green spaces, during this period.

The urbanization challenges had direct and lasting impacts on Bangalore's urban green spaces: Loss of Green Spaces: Green areas, like parks and vacant lands, were converted into commercial and residential developments, reducing the accessible green spaces.

Tree-felling and Green-cover Decline: Trees were removed for infrastructure and real estate projects, causing a decline in vegetation and green- cover, despite effects of the Tree Preservation Act and other similar policies. Lake Encroachments and Pollution: Lakes faced encroachment and pollution issues, with Bellandur Lake symbolizing the challenges at its peak, with the instances of lake eutrophication and pollution, frothing the lake. Traffic Congestion and Pollution: Urbanization and vehicle ownership led to severe traffic congestion and air pollution, impacting both green spaces and the residents' quality of life. Urban Sprawl: Uncontrolled urban sprawl converted agricultural lands, the seasonal lake-beds and open spaces into residential and commercial zones, further diminishing green areas. Urban Heat Island Effect: Rising temperatures resulted from concrete development, reduced green cover, reduced water-spread areas and increased energy consumption for cooling. Biodiversity Loss: Natural habitats were fragmented or destroyed, causing biodiversity loss affecting native flora and fauna, with the lakes and their green buffers which were home to many migratory birds and other species.

Influencing Factors and the Causes of Transformation

Research findings from "Local Assessment of Bangalore: Graying and Greening in Bangalore – Impacts of Urbanization on Ecosystems, Ecosystem Services and Biodiversity" (Sudhira, & Nagendra, 2013), suggest that population growth, rapid urban sprawl, and land use policies that favored development, played pivotal roles in reshaping the city's green landscape. Additionally, the significance of preserving green spaces was underscored by research on the "Carbon Sequestration Potential of Urban Trees" (Ugle Pimpalkhute, Rao, Ramachandra, 2010).

The numerous factors that contributed to the transformation of Bangalore's urban greens are as follows:

Rapid Urbanization: Population growth and urban sprawl, increased demand for residential, commercial, and industrial areas, being catered to, often by encroaching upon the blue and green covers of the city. **Land Use Policies:** Policy shifts favored real estate and commercial development, converting green areas into built-up spaces, increasing the concretized areas, within urban limits. **Infrastructure Development:** Transport expansion necessitated tree removal, resulting in diminishing of greenery. **Real Estate Boom:** Construction of complexes occupied available open and green areas. **Population Growth:** Housing demand led to open space conversion to housing complexes and townships. **Green Infrastructure Gaps:** Incomplete planning for green corridors, urban forests and greenways, led to lack of execution of the same. **Sustainability Lapses:** Inadequate urban planning prioritized development over sustainability. **Climate Change Risks:** Vulnerability to climate impacts, affected green space health. **Industrialization:** Growth altered land use, impacted green areas. **Infrastructure Projects:** Large projects required green cover removal. **Waste Mismanagement:** Pollution from improper waste disposal harmed green spaces. **Planning Deficiencies:** Inadequate planning, resulted in unchecked urban sprawl and encroachments on urban greens.

Associated Policies and Government Initiatives

The efforts to mitigate the impact of urbanization on the urban greens included government policies and initiatives. Urban planners and policymakers in Bangalore encountered intricate challenges, in attempts to balance the city's development with the preservation and enhancement of urban greens. Citizen activism and environmental awareness significantly influenced policies and initiatives aimed at rejuvenating these greens.(Chandran, 2016). Local and state governments' efforts had a substantial impact, although implementation hurdles remained. Key policies and frameworks included: **Tree Preservation Act:** Enacted in 1976, this legislation aimed to safeguard trees in Bangalore by regulating tree felling and transplantation, protecting the city's tree cover, as discussed in "Citizen Matters"(Atreya, 2018). However, enforcement and compliance challenges often hindered its effectiveness.

Green Building Initiatives: Bangalore actively promoted sustainable construction practices through certifications like LEED, IGBC, etc., reducing the environmental footprint of buildings and fostering eco-friendly urban development. **Lake Conservation:** Government-led projects, including the "Namma Bengaluru" campaign, aimed to revive and protect the city's lakes. While some projects made progress, issues of pollution and encroachments continued to persist in certain lakes. **Urban Forestry:** The Bangalore Urban Forestry Project aimed to boost green cover through tree planting and afforestation efforts. These initiatives positively contributed to increasing green spaces but faced challenges related to land availability and maintenance. **Master Plans:** The Bangalore Development Authority (BDA) and Bangalore Metropolitan Region Development Authority (BMRDA) integrated provisions for green spaces, parks and open areas within urban development plans. However, the implementation of these varied across different zones.

Public Green Spaces: The Bruhat Bengaluru Mahanagara Palike (BBMP) focused on developing and maintaining public green spaces, including parks and playgrounds, throughout the city. Some notable examples of these are Lalbagh Botanical Garden, Cubbon Park, Freedom Park, Golf Course, etc. Urban

Biodiversity Policy: Bangalore introduced an Urban Biodiversity Policy to conserve and protect biodiversity within urban areas, which aimed to integrate biodiversity considerations into urban planning and development. The above policies, while impactful in certain aspects, faced ongoing challenges for full implementation and enforcement, highlighting the complex nature of preserving and enhancing urban greens in Bangalore.

Inferences

The success of these policies and frameworks varied, with some achieving positive outcomes. However, persistent challenges arose due to factors like rapid urbanization, population growth and the need for stronger enforcement mechanisms. Inferences drawn from this case study underline the importance of comprehensive urban planning that balances development and environmental preservation. Bangalore's evolution serves as a vivid example of the challenges, urbanization poses to urban greens and the pressing need to safeguard these spaces for ecological balance and the well-being of the city's residents. The findings from "Mapping urban green spaces based on remote sensing data" (Vatseva, et al., 2016) emphasize on the role of advanced techniques like remote sensing in tracking and managing urban green spaces, to create more sustainable cities. As Bangalore continues to grow and evolve, these lessons will be instrumental in shaping its urban future.

Case Study 2 – Singapore

Figure 2. NDVI Temporal Analysis of Singapore City for 2003, 2013, 2023

The Urban Greens and the Impact of Urbanisation on them

Urbanization in Singapore has led to a remarkable transformation of the city's green spaces. Collaborative efforts between landscape architects, the National Parks Board and researchers have shaped a biodiverse urban environment. Projects like Bishan-Ang Mo Kio Park and Jurong Lake Gardens have restored

natural habitats and created recreational spaces. The Active, Beautiful, Clean Waters Program has revitalized urban water bodies for community bonding. Green architecture and their policies address urban heat and biodiversity loss. The Green Plan 2030 aims to expand green areas and plant trees for future sustainability. Singapore's commitment to its urban greens, makes it one of the world's greenest cities, promoting a healthier and more sustainable urban lifestyle for its residents (Joson, 2022).

Influencing Factors and the Causes of Transformation

Singapore's transformation into a true "Garden City" is influenced by innovative urban planning, exemplified in the article "This City Aims to Be the World's Greenest" (Kolczak, 2017; Joson, 2022). The city's remarkable economic growth made it achieve a skyline, dominated by towering structures. But, it now focuses on integrating nature into its urban fabric, while continuing to expand. The key factors driving this green evolution include: **Mandatory Green Building:** Since 2008, Singapore has enforced mandatory green building practices, leading to the proliferation of green roofs, cascading vertical gardens and verdant walls in all its new urban developments. **Visionary Leadership:** The leadership of urban innovators like Cheong Koon Hean, CEO of the Housing and Development Board, has played a pivotal role. Her vision has reshaped the skyline through projects like Marina Bay, renowned for its gardens, and the Jurong Lake District, a thriving business hub. **Community-centric Urbanism:** Singapore's public housing emphasizes community-centric towns and amenities, promoting a high quality of life for its residents. **Cultural Diversity:** Singapore's cosmopolitan character, blends its cultural and architectural legacies from the Chinese, Indian, Malay and Western influences, while creating identity to its unique urban fabric. **Green Space Expansion:** An incentive program which encourages, replacing ground-level greenery lost to development, with high-rise terraces and gardens. This creates additional spaces for recreation and community gatherings. For instance, the Pinnacle at Duxton stands as a prime example of vertical greenery and urban fitness facilities. This commitment to green urbanism and innovative thinking distinguishes Singapore as a thriving urban area and sets it as an example for sustainable livable cities.

Associated Policies and Government Initiatives

Singapore's commitment to green urbanism is fortified by robust policies and government initiatives, as evidenced in the article, "Natural Green Walking City" (Kolczak, 2017). These initiatives include:

Expansive Green Coverage: Singapore has diligently pursued its "Garden City" vision, dedicating 46.5% of its land to green spaces, with nearly 30% tree canopy coverage, making it one of the world's greenest cities. The city-state boasts over 300 kilometers of green corridors within its 'Park Connector Network.'

Emphasis on Sustainable Transport: Due to its compact size, Singapore prioritizes public transport, cycling and walking over private vehicles. These modes of transport are seamlessly integrated with Urban Green Space (UGS) development and protection policies. The Park Connector Network, initiated in 1991, plays a pivotal role in promoting green mobility corridors. **Green Infrastructure Priority:** Singapore promotes green infrastructure in urban development through initiatives like the LUSH (Landscaping for Urban Spaces and High-Rises) Programme, emphasizing on green walls and buildings, creating urban walkability.

Shaded Walkways and Pedestrian Crossings: In response to Singapore's tropical climate, the city has invested in constructing 200 kilometers of sheltered walkways, ensuring pedestrian comfort from sun and rain, especially in housing, commercial and transport areas. **Inclusive Transport Vision:** Singapore's "Walk Cycle Ride SG" envisions inclusive urban transport, with a focus on enhancing walking routes and environments for all. **Public Engagement:** Engaging citizens in all its initiatives, has been pivotal since Singapore's inception. Government Initiatives like the Civic District Tree Trail and protection of trees involve the public, fostering a sense of ownership and responsibility among them, to create a greener Singapore. These policies and practices underscore Singapore's remarkable commitment to preserving and expanding its urban green spaces while promoting sustainable and inclusive urban mobility.

Inferences

Singapore's urbanization drives green spaces. Projects like Bishan-Ang Mo Kio Park and green architecture combat urban issues. Policies and public engagement foster greener, livable cities, aiming for more sustainable urban environments.

Case Study 3 - Abu Dhabi

Figure 3. NDVI Temporal Analysis of Abu Dhabi city for 2003, 2013, 2023

4.3.1. The Urban Greens and the Impact of Urbanisation on them

The urbanization in Abu Dhabi between 2003-2023, had a mixed impact on urban greens (Madden, 2015; Al Ramahi, 2023). During this period, the city saw a remarkable expansion of green spaces, with the development of parks and recreational areas, elevating the city's quality of life and also creating a new urban image for itself (Al Ramahi, 2023). Preservation of natural habitats, including mangroves and wetlands, became a crucial aspect of Abu Dhabi's commitment to biodiversity conservation (Madden, 2015).

However, the process of urbanization invited its own impacts with new challenges. Land use changes resulted in the conversion of green areas for urban development, contributing to the urban heat island effect (Abulibdeh 2021). Abu Dhabi responded with sustainable development initiatives that integrated green infrastructure and green building practices into its urban planning guidelines. Landscape design incorporated elements like green roofs, enhancing both aesthetics and environmental sustainability. The city also witnessed growing environmental awareness, influencing government policies and fostering public participation, to shape its green future (National Committee on Sustainable Development Goals, 2017).

The key impacts on Abu Dhabi's urban greens include Expansion of Green Spaces, Preservation of Natural Habitats, Land Use Changes, Urban Heat Island Effect, Biodiversity Conservation, Sustainable Development Initiatives, Landscape Design and Green Infrastructure, Environmental Awareness, etc.

Influencing Factors and the Causes of Transformation

Factors such as rapid urbanization, infrastructure development and economic growth played pivotal roles in shaping urban greens in the emirates cities, balancing the city's growth and environmental sustainability (Awad, & Jung, 2021). Government policies and climate change mitigation strategies further influenced these changes (Awad, & Jung, 2021). Public participation and a commitment to biodiversity conservation and sustainability were key drivers of the city's evolving urban greens initiatives (National Committee on Sustainable Development Goals, 2017).

This case study illustrates the intricate interplay of factors and proactive measures required to balance urbanization with environmental conservation and sustainable development in Abu Dhabi.

In general, the following factors influenced and caused changes in the urban greens of Abu Dhabi: **Rapid Urbanization:** The city experienced rapid population growth and urban expansion, leading to increased demand for land and infrastructure development. **Infrastructure Development:** Major infrastructure projects, including road expansions and construction, often required the clearance of green areas, altering the city's landscape. **Economic Development:** Abu Dhabi's economic growth attracted investment and development, impacting the allocation of land for commercial and residential purposes. **Government Policies:** Urban planning and development policies, as well as environmental regulations, influenced the preservation or alteration of green spaces. **Environmental Awareness:** Growing awareness of environmental issues influenced efforts to protect and enhance urban greens, promoting sustainable development. **Biodiversity Conservation:** Conservation initiatives aimed to protect natural habitats and promote biodiversity within the urban environment. **Climate Change Mitigation:** Efforts to address climate change included urban greening projects to mitigate the urban heat island effect and reduce carbon emissions. **Public Participation:** Community engagement and advocacy was instrumental in influencing government decisions, regarding the management and development of urban greens.

Associated Policies and Government initiatives

The "Plan Abu Dhabi 2030" emphasizes on the importance of preserving the city's unique ecological context, which is defined by its location, at the interface of the desert and the sea (Government of Abu Dhabi, 2023). It proposes an Environmental Framework Plan aimed at preserving vital ecologies, including mangroves, seagrass beds and migratory bird habitats. This plan advocates the establishment of a National Park System adjacent to the city, where development would be forbidden, and activities carefully regulated to protect these critical ecological resources. Additionally, the plan introduces the concept of a 'Green Gradient' and a 'Sand Belt' to control urban sprawl and protect the environment, with emphasis on Desert Eco-Villages as development areas. Moreover, 'Desert Fingers' serve as undeveloped buffers to safeguard the desert's connection with the Gulf, preventing endless sprawl along the corridor, linking to Dubai. These policies and initiatives aim to balance economic development and ecological preservation within Abu Dhabi's urban framework.

Inferences

The urbanization of Abu Dhabi from 2003 to 2023 led to both positive and negative impacts on its urban greens. On one hand, there was a significant expansion of green spaces and a commitment to preserving natural habitats like mangroves and wetlands. This expansion improved the quality of life of its residents and demonstrated the city's dedication to biodiversity conservation. However, urbanization also posed challenges, including the conversion of green areas for urban development, leading to the urban heat island effect. Abu Dhabi addressed these challenges by implementing sustainable development initiatives, integrating green infrastructure into urban planning and embracing green building practices. The city's

landscape design incorporated elements like green roofs, to enhance both aesthetics and environmental sustainability. Environmental awareness grew among the population, influencing government policies and encouraging public participation to shape the city's green future. Overall, Abu Dhabi's approach demonstrates a commitment to harmonize urbanization with environmental sustainability.

Conclusion

The Temporal Analysis of Bangalore between 2003 and 2013, indicates the reduction in green spaces due to urbanization, while showing increased urban areas, in the outskirts of the city. But from 2013 to 2023, the overall green spaces increased within the city as well as in the suburbs. As far as Singapore is concerned, we can see a significant increase in its green spaces from 2003 to 2013, whereas it remains almost stagnant from 2013 to 2023. A similar case is observed in Abu Dhabi. Since this is a desert region, hardly any vegetation is grown. We can see negligible green spaces in 2003 but in 2013 and 2023, green urban patches are pronounced.

The policies of all the three cities, considered for study, have been made with an intent to preserve, promote and enhance Urban Green Spaces, highlighting its importance for a sustainable growth and also to combat the adverse effects, which may not be possible to mitigate, if the Urban Greens are not taken care of. The various public initiatives and government frameworks have been a result of this awareness. The policies initiated by the government authorities of the chosen three cities, are adequate to conserve and sustain their urban greens, if followed and implemented with responsibility. Periodic checks can be mandatory, for timely evaluation of the current urban scenarios, and revision of the existing policies and frameworks in accordance. GIS and Remote Sensing can be effective tools for the accurate assessment of the shrinking Green Footprints in urban areas, and implementation of the need-based recommendations, as and when required.

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